

Azeotropic distillation for 1-propanol dehydration with diisopropyl ether as entrainer: equilibrium data and process simulation.

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ABSTRACT

Azeotropic distillation process is widely used to separate non-ideal binary mixtures into their constituent pure components. 1-Propanol dehydration was used as case study and diisopropyl ether was analysed as possible entrainer in an azeotropic distillation. The separation of some alcohols from their aqueous solution is a challenging task because these aqueous mixture forms minimum boiling azeotrope.

In this way, isobaric vapor-liquid and vapour-liquid-liquid equilibrium data were measured for the 1-propanol+ water + diisopropyl ether ternary mixture at 101.3 kPa. The data were correlated by NRTL and UNIQUAC models.

A separation sequence (a decanter and a single-feed distillation column) for 1-propanol dehydration using diisopropyl ether was proposed. The simulation of the separation sequence was carried out satisfactorily by Aspen Hysys® using the thermodynamic model NRTL with the binary parameters obtained in this work. Moreover, the effect of temperature decantation was investigated in order to reduce the energy demand of the process.

KEYWORDS

1-Propanol dehydration, diisopropyl ether, azeotropic distillation, computer simulation.

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INTRODUCTION

A growing demand for energy and the negative impact that fossil fuels have on the environment make it imperative the research for other sources of energy. One of the proposals is the use of alcohols as biofuels derived from renewable sources.^{1, 2} Among these alcohols is the 1-propanol, which can be converted into diesel fuel by esterification reaction³. However, the separation of these alcohols from their aqueous solution is a challenging task because these aqueous mixtures form minimum boiling azeotropes, which prevent the separation of such mixtures by simple distillation. To solve this problem, membrane technology⁴ or nonconventional distillations processes have been proposed, including extractive distillation (ED)⁵ and azeotropic distillation (AD).⁶ These distillations are based on the addition of a third component called entrainer that alters the relative volatility of the components of the original mixture.

In an ED process, the entrainer does not form an azeotrope with any of the components of the mixture to be separated. On the other hand, in an AD process, the addition of the third compound forms an additional azeotrope to carry out the desired separation. Depending on the number of phases present in the new azeotrope, the AD will be homogeneous (a unique liquid phase) or heterogeneous (two liquid phases). In both cases, it is essential to know the vapor-liquid equilibrium (VLE) data to a properly design a distillation sequence. In addition, in cases with more than one liquid phase, the knowledge of the vapor-liquid-liquid equilibrium (VLLE) data is also required.

In previous works, several organic compounds were proposed as the entrainer in an ED (ethylene glycol⁷ and isobutyl alcohol⁸) or AD (propyl acetate⁹) process for dehydration of 1-propanol. In this paper, and as part of our continuing research work, diisopropyl ether is selected as possible entrainer for an azeotropic distillation capable of separating 1-propanol/water mixture. In this case, a hybrid separation sequence of a decanter and a single-feed distillation column is proposed.

The first stage was the gathering of isobaric VLE and VLLE data of the ternary system 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) at 101.3 kPa. Experimental VLE and VLLE data of this ternary system is available in the literature¹⁰ and have been compared with those obtained in this work. Ternary experimental data were found thermodynamically consistent after successfully passing the Wisniak and Tamir¹¹ modification of McDermott-Ellis test.¹²

In the next stage, binary parameters for the NRTL¹³ and UNIQUAC¹⁴ local composition models of the ternary system were obtained by correlating experimental phase equilibrium data. Then, the best model was selected to use in the simulation of azeotropic distillation process. In this way, Aspen Hysys® v9.0 was selected as a process simulator for both its simulation capabilities and its ability to incorporate calculation using the spreadsheet tool.

THERMODYNAMIC ANALYSIS

VLE of partially miscible liquid mixtures involves simultaneously three phase equilibrium conditions in the two-liquid phase region. On the one hand, the VLE involves the liquid-liquid equilibrium (LLE) of both phases and on the other hand, the VLE of the liquid phases with the vapor phase. The condition LLE is expressed as follows:

$$(\gamma_i x_i)^I = (\gamma_i x_i)^{II} \quad (1)$$

where I and II represent the liquid phases, γ_i the activity coefficient and x_i the molar liquid fraction of the component i . And the VLE:

$$y_i = \frac{\gamma_i P_i^o}{\Phi_i P} x_i^I = \frac{\gamma_i P_i^o}{\Phi_i P} x_i^{II} \quad (2)$$

where P_i^o the saturated vapor pressure of the component i , calculated by the equation and parameters reported in DIPPR¹⁵ tables and listed in Table 1, P is the total pressure and Φ_i is the fugacity coefficients quotient multiplied by the Poynting correlation factor:

$$\Phi_i = \frac{\hat{\phi}_i}{\phi_i^o} \exp \frac{-V_i^L (P - P_i^o)}{RT} \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\phi}_i$ is the fugacity coefficient of component i in the vapor phase, ϕ_i^o is the fugacity coefficient of pure saturated liquid i and V_i^L is the molar liquid volume of component i calculated by the Rackett equation.¹⁶

The fugacity coefficient of component i in the vapor phase can be calculated from the second virial coefficient, B :

$$\ln \hat{\phi}_i = \frac{P}{RT} \left(2 \sum_{j=1}^N y_j B_{ij} - B \right) \quad (4)$$

where B_{ij} is the cross second virial coefficient.

With respect to the fugacity coefficient of a pure saturated liquid, ϕ_i^o , it can be obtained assuming as standard state the pure component at the pressure and temperature of the solution.

$$\ln \phi_i^o = \frac{B_{ii}P_i^o}{RT} \quad (5)$$

where B_{ii} is the second virial coefficient of the pure component.

The virial coefficients B_{ii} and B_{ij} were estimated by the method of Hayden and O'Connell¹⁷ using the molecular parameters suggested by Prausnitz et al.¹⁸

Given eqs 1-5, the follow equation is used to obtain the activity coefficients:

$$\ln \gamma_i = \ln \frac{y_i P}{x_i P_i^o} + \frac{(B_{ii} - V_i^L)(P - P_i^o)}{RT} + \frac{P}{2RT} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n y_j y_k (2\delta_{ji} - \delta_{jk}) \quad (6)$$

where δ_{ij} is obtained from

$$\delta_{ij} = 2B_{ij} - B_{jj} - B_{ii} \quad (7)$$

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Chemicals. 1-Propanol (>0.990 mass fraction) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich and both water (water for chromatography LiChrosolv) and diisopropyl ether (>0.990 mass fraction) were supplied by Merck. No significant impurities were found after analyzing all chemicals by chromatography. As a result, no purification methods were applied. A Karl Fischer volumetric automatic titrator (Metrohm, 701 KF Titrino) was used to determine the water content. The results showed a negligible amount of water in pure organic components, even so, both chemicals were dried over molecular sieves (Aldrich, type 4 Å, 1.6 mm pellets).

Apparatus and Procedure. The experimental procedure used there to analyze the phase equilibria is described in previous works.^{19,20}

The equilibrium temperature was measured with a digital Hart Scientific thermometer model 1502A and a Pt 100 probe Hart Scientific model 5622 calibrated at the ENAC-accredited Spanish *Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial*. The accuracy is estimated to be ± 0.01 K. The temperature probe was checked against the ice and steam points of distilled water. A Fisher M101 pressure control system was used to measure and control the pressure and the heating power. The measured pressure in the still was 101.3 ± 0.1 kPa. The manometer was calibrated using the vapour pressure of ultrapure water.

Analysis of the different phases was carried out by gas chromatography (GC). The sampling of the vapour phase was carried out using a VW Type, 6-port heated valve from Valco Instruments Co., which injected the sample directly into the GC. The connecting tube wall was overheated with a resistance tape controlled by a digital potentiometer so that the vapour becomes superheated and condensation is avoided. For the sampling of the liquid phase in the heterogeneous region, a small amount of the liquid coming from the separation chamber of the equipment was diverted to a closed heat-insulated test tube. In this tube, the dispersed liquid phases enter and separate into two phases (approximately 1 day) at constant temperature (slightly lower than the mixture bubble point) since the tube is placed in a block heater SBH200DC from Stuart Scientific. A sample of each phase was taken and placed in a vial with a small amount of ethanol. The addition of ethanol prevents phase separation effects when changing the temperature after separation of phases. The composition of the sampled liquid phases and vapor phase were determined using a CE Instruments GC 8000 Top GC, after calibration with gravimetrically prepared standard solutions. A thermal conductivity detector (TCD) was used together with 80/100 Porapak Q 3 m \times 1/8 in column. The GC response peaks were treated with Chrom-Card for Windows. The optimum operation conditions were: injection temperature, 473 K; oven temperature, 373 K; detector temperature, 433 K and detector current 220 mA and the helium flow rate was 40 ml/min. Very good peak separation was achieved under these conditions and calibration analyses were used to convert the peak area ratio to the mass composition of the sample. The standard deviation in the mole fraction was usually less than 0.002.

Phase Equilibrium Data. Equilibrium temperature T , the liquid phase mole fraction of component i , x_i , and the vapor phase mole fraction of component i , y_i , were obtained for the 1-propanol + water + diisopropyl ether ternary system. All measurements were made under isobaric conditions. Table 2 lists the experimental data of VLE and Table 3 the experimental VLLE data. Moreover, Figure 1 represents the graphical ternary diagram of 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3), that include the experimental vapor data and the nonisothermal tie lines of the two liquid phases. In order to compare acquired experimental data, the Piennar et al.¹⁰ data have also been plotted in Figure 1. As can be seen, water and diisopropyl ether are partially miscible and 1-propanol and diisopropyl ether are completely miscible. In addition, there are no significant differences between our data and the data of

Piennar et al. The thermodynamic consistency was checked with the Wisniak and Tamir¹¹ modification of McDermott-Ellis test.¹²

Data Correlation. Experimental data have been correlated in order to obtain the parameters of NRTL and UNIQUAC models. It is always preferable to obtain a unique set of parameters for each model. This means that the same parameters have to be capable of estimating correctly the VLE data and the binodal curve. Therefore, the suitable way is correlate jointly both kinds of data. So, the objective function (FO) used to correlate all the experimental data is the following:

$$FO = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\left| \frac{T_i^{exp} - T_i^{calc}}{T_i^{exp}} \right| + \sum_{j=1}^2 |y_{ji}^{exp} - y_{ji}^{calc}| + \sum_{k=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 |x_{ji}^{k,exp} - x_{ji}^{k,calc}| \right) \quad (8)$$

where N is the total number of points, superscripts *exp* and *calc* refer to experimental and calculated values, respectively, and the subscript k refers to the number of the liquid phase.

The nonrandomness parameter α_{ij} of the NRTL model was fixed at 0.3. The volume and surface parameters used in the UNIQUAC model were taken from DECHEMA.²¹ Table 4 shows the binary interaction parameters obtained after correlation. In this way, deviations are listed in Table 5.

To compare the VLE and VLLE data of the system 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) obtained in this work with those from literature,¹⁰ these reported data have been estimated using the NRTL model with the parameters given in Table 4. The estimation has been made with a bubble temperature calculation and the average deviations between calculated and experimental values from temperature and vapor phase composition for VLE data and from temperature, vapor and liquid phases composition for VLLE data are shown in Table 6. According to the results of this comparison, a good agreement with the data of Piennar et al.¹⁰ is obtained; similar, and in some cases better, to the deviations obtained in the correlation of their own data.

As it is explained in the Simulation Process item, it is proposed a new separation sequence, based on a hybrid extraction-distillation system. In that respect, to verify the liquid-liquid equilibria (LLE) obtained from NRTL parameters given in Table 4, the average absolute deviations (AAD) obtained of the experimental data of Hwang et al.²² have been calculated. The AAD between the calculated and experimental mole fraction were 0.018 and 0.019 in the aqueous phase and 0.027 and 0.042 in the organic for 1-propanol and water, respectively.

Azeotropic Behaviour. In Figure 1, it can be seen that all of the vapor-phase lie below the corresponding tie line. Consequently, no straight line exists in the phase envelope, except at the binary water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) azeotropic point, upon which corresponding aqueous liquid, organic liquids, and vapor phase compositions are found. This justifies the absence of a ternary heterogeneous azeotrope, as is also verified in the previously published data.¹⁰In this case, it is impossible to dehydrate aqueous 1-propanol via conventional heterogeneous azeotropic distillation when using diisopropyl ether as an entrainer, but an alternative AD could be considered. In that sense, a good prediction of the azeotropes present in the system is very important for the process simulation. The values of compositions and temperature of these azeotropes are listed in Table 7. In addition to the experimental data, Table 7 also reported azeotropic calculated data with NRTL and UNIQUAC models with the parameters given in Table 4. According to calculated azeotropic data from Table 7, both models make a good prediction of the 1-propanol (1) + water (2) and water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) binary azeotrope. Nevertheless, UNIQUAC model predicts a 1-propanol (1) + diisopropyl ether (3) binary azeotrope, where from the compilation of Gmhelting et al.^{25, 26} it is also clear that no binary azeotrope exists between 1-propanol and diisopropyl ether. Therefore, the NRTL model is better to predict the azeotropic behavior and has been used to the process simulation.

PROCESS SIMULATION

Azeotropic Distillation Sequence. Although, as it is said by of Pienaar et al.,¹⁰ that it is impossible to dehydrate aqueous n-propanol via conventional heterogeneous azeotropic distillation when using diisopropyl ether as an entrainer, however an azeotropic distillation sequence can be proposed. According to Figure 2, the process consists of a single distillation column, with the consequent saving in the costs derived from the immobilization and the operating costs compared to a heterogeneous azeotropic distillation where two distillation columns are required.

First, before carrying out the distillation, the stream to be separated (F1) and a recycle stream (D1), rich in diisopropyl ether, are mixed. In addition, in order to recover the amount of solvent lost in the process, a stream of fresh diisopropyl ether is also added. The mixture of these streams results in a heterogeneous mixture, so that water can be separated by decantation. The slope of the tie lines of this system causes that the aqueous stream that is obtained after the

decanting has a high water content, close to 98% molar, as shown in the ternary diagram of Figure 3. This option makes it possible to dispense with the water purification column, which was present in the distillation sequence for the dehydration of 1-propanol using ethylene glycol⁷ or isobutyl alcohol⁸ as an entrainer.

The feed of the azeotropic column is the organic stream (xrich) from the decanter with a composition lying within the distillation region where the stable node is the 1-propanol vertex. This allows to obtain by distillation a residue stream of 1-propanol (B1) and a distillate with an ether-rich composition, which is recirculated to the initial decanter.

Simulation and Optimization. The sequence proposed above was simulated and optimized using Aspen Hysys® v9.0, a computer simulator developed by Aspen Technologies. The thermodynamic model used in the simulation was NRTL with the parameters listed in Table 4. The 1-propanol mole fraction in the feed was set at 0.4. This value was chosen because it is close enough to the azeotropic point ($x_1 = 0.43$). The rest of process specifications were the mass flow and temperature of the initial stream, the pressure of the column, the purity and component recovery of 1-propanol and the purity of water. The values of these variables are listed in Table 8. Figure 4 illustrates the azeotropic distillation process.

In order to obtain a water mass fraction of 0.96 it has been evaluated two options, modifying the temperature of the decanter, taking into account the great influence of this in the liquid-liquid equilibrium. On the one hand, it is fixed a decantation temperature of 10°C (option 1) and in that case, the entrainer flow rate must be 50 kmol/h. On the other hand, if it is fixed a decantation temperature of 30°C (option 2) the entrainer flow rate necessary is 90 kmol/h.

The azeotropic distillation column, for both decanter options, was optimized using Aspen Hysys® software calculating the number of stages, reflux ratio, and optimum feed locations where the capital cost and operating cost are minimized in the distillation column. To carry out the optimization, we studied different cases varying the number of stages, selecting in each case the optimum feed location that minimized the reboiler heat duty. In the Support Information document (Tables S1 and S2), the data obtained for each of the cases are presented. Figure 5 shows the NQ curves, plots of reboiler heat duty Q and the number of stages with the optimal feed location N , versus total number of stages for both decanter options where it can be seen a clear minimums. As can be seen in Table 9, the reboiler heat duty of option 2 is more than twice that required in option 1, and therefore it would seem obvious to think that option 1 is the optimal one. However, the cooling costs in the decanter of option 1 will be higher than option

2, so it was decided to make an estimate of all the process variable cost of each of the options. The process variable cost, which corresponds to utilities consumptions, was calculated using the utilities prices of Table 10. As can be seen in Figure 6, the cooling costs of option 1 are greater than those of option 2, although the heating costs are the predominant ones, therefore the optimal option would be to work with a temperature of 10°C in the decanter. In addition, if we calculate CO₂ emissions, supposing that the heating demand is supplied by gas natural (CO₂ factor = $5.589 \cdot 10^{-8}$ kg/J for US-EPA-Rule-E9-5711) the CO₂ emission increases by 40% from option 1 (0.287 kg CO₂/kg feed) to option 2 (0.686 kg CO₂/kg feed).

Finally, the simulation and optimization of the proposed process has been compared with the results obtained in the dehydration of 1-propanol by extractive distillation using the ethylene glycol as entrainer [7]. If the operating costs are compared, both utilities (steam and cooling duties) are higher in this hybrid extraction-distillation system (heat duty reboiler = $6.52 \cdot 10^5$ kJ/h and heat duty condenser = $6.84 \cdot 10^5$ kJ/h) than in extractive distillation process with ethylene glycol (heat duty reboiler = $3.70 \cdot 10^5$ kJ/h and heat duty condenser = $5.11 \cdot 10^3$ kJ/h). This increase in energy demands is due to the fact that the energy consumption at reboiler of the distillation column become high because the top vapor stream (D1) is much larger than the flow rate of B1 stream. In addition, the cooling costs would also be much higher because it is necessary to use refrigerated water instead of cooling water processes. With regard to the capital cost, the hybrid extraction-distillation proposed process will probably be much more attractive than the separation by extractive distillation [7] because in this case, the recovery of the entrainer is done by decanting and in extractive distillation it is used a distillation column, which is much more energy demanding. Therefore, to opt for a separation technique, it would be necessary to carry out an exhaustive economic evaluation of both processes, taking into account both capital costs and operating costs.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of diisopropyl ether as entrainer for an azeotropic distillation to 1-propanol dehydration was proposed. Isobaric VLE and VLLE data were measured for 1-propanol + water + diisopropyl ether ternary system at 101.3 kPa. The NRTL and UNIQUAC models were used to correlate the data of the 1-propanol + water + diisopropyl ether system.

This paper aims to carry out a study on the dehydration of 1-propanol by an azeotropic distillation sequence consisting of a decanter and a single-feed distillation column. Therefore, a

comparison between two different temperatures of decantation was made. Aspen Hysys v9.0 software was used to carry out the simulation and thermodynamic calculations were done with the NRTL model parameters obtained in this paper. Results showed that it is possible to use diisopropyl ether to separate 1-propanol and water. The economical evaluation of process variable cost found a decantation at 10°C and an azeotropic column with 20 ideal stages the best option for carrying out the separation.

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Tables

Table 1. Vapor Pressure Parameters

compound	A_i	B_i	C_i	D_i	E_i
1-propanol (1)	73.649	-8295.9	-8.9096	$1.8197 \cdot 10^{-6}$	2
water (2)	76.649	-7258.2	-7.3037	$4.1653 \cdot 10^{-6}$	2
diisopropyl ether (3)	41.631	-4668.7	-2.8551	$6.3693 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1

Parameters and vapor pressure equation obtained from DIPPR tables¹⁵

Vapor pressure equation: $\ln P^o(\text{Pa}) = A + B/T(\text{K}) + C \ln T(\text{K}) + D (T(\text{K}))^E$

Table 2. VLE data for 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) ternary system at 101.3 kPa.

x_1	x_2	y_1	y_2	T (K)
0.333	0.163	0.104	0.215	339.62
0.369	0.239	0.115	0.238	340.40
0.418	0.252	0.131	0.242	341.71
0.423	0.301	0.140	0.262	342.27
0.483	0.084	0.193	0.086	343.30
0.534	0.039	0.230	0.065	346.21
0.547	0.243	0.197	0.253	346.24
0.537	0.298	0.201	0.289	347.50
0.630	0.066	0.287	0.090	348.37
0.429	0.524	0.253	0.408	349.73
0.692	0.099	0.307	0.130	350.64
0.606	0.282	0.275	0.317	350.89
0.516	0.421	0.269	0.394	351.75
0.538	0.401	0.284	0.399	352.60
0.737	0.043	0.382	0.071	352.61
0.717	0.168	0.347	0.246	353.05
0.666	0.240	0.335	0.311	353.32
0.743	0.161	0.390	0.251	354.76
0.418	0.563	0.311	0.487	356.07
0.741	0.185	0.445	0.286	356.35
0.508	0.473	0.365	0.502	357.42
0.627	0.348	0.392	0.444	357.74
0.733	0.234	0.505	0.380	360.37
0.833	0.132	0.556	0.278	361.11
0.822	0.156	0.583	0.304	361.88
0.907	0.070	0.715	0.181	364.60

Table 3. VLLE data for 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) ternary system at 101.3 kPa.

Organic-rich phase, x_i^I		Aqueous-rich phase, x_i^{II}		Vapor phase, y_i		T (K)
x_1	x_2	x_1	x_2	y_1	y_2	
0.030	0.066	0.003	0.996	0.016	0.232	351.78
0.125	0.114	0.014	0.979	0.044	0.242	351.90
0.204	0.126	0.023	0.964	0.070	0.246	352.64
0.247	0.154	0.024	0.970	0.080	0.257	352.77
0.306	0.208	0.029	0.966	0.088	0.261	352.80
0.363	0.314	0.036	0.959	0.097	0.264	352.93
0.380	0.354	0.036	0.962	0.123	0.287	354.70

Table 4. Parameters for NRTL and UNIQUAC models obtained for the ternary system 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3).

System $i + j$	NRTL			UNIQUAC ^a	
	Δg_{ij} (J·mol ⁻¹)	Δg_{ji} (J·mol ⁻¹)	α_{ij}	Δu_{ij} (J·mol ⁻¹)	Δu_{ji} (J·mol ⁻¹)
1+2	-129.95	8313.90	0.3	635.14	1360.40
1+3	372.73	2803.20	0.3	-1474.23	3501.44
2+3	13763.74	6489.47	0.3	648.86	5572.73

^a Volume and surface parameters from DECHEMA²¹

Table 5. Correlation Statics for the NRTL and UNIQUAC models from the system 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3).

	AAD T^a (K)	AAD y_1^b	AAD y_2^b	AAD x_1^{Ic}	AAD x_2^{Ic}	AAD x_1^{IIc}	AAD x_2^{IIc}
NRTL Model							
VLE data	0.39	0.012	0.011				
VLLE data	1.75	0.009	0.011	0.014	0.018	0.003	0.004
UNIQUAC Model							
VLE data	0.81	0.022	0.014				
VLLE data	1.60	0.010	0.010	0.007	0.019	0.003	0.004

^a Average absolute deviation in temperature.

^b Average absolute deviation in vapor phase composition.

^c Average absolute deviation in liquid phase composition.

Table 6. Estimation of VLE and VLLE data from literature¹⁰ using NRTL model with parameters from Table 4 for the system 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3).

	AAD T^a (K)	AAD y_1^b	AAD y_2^b	AAD x_1^{Ic}	AAD x_2^{Ic}	AAD x_1^{IIc}	AAD x_2^{IIc}
VLE data	1.24	0.070	0.031				
VLLE data	0.45	0.030	0.019	0.041	0.051	0.010	0.011

^a Average absolute deviation in temperature.

^b Average absolute deviation in vapor phase composition.

^c Average absolute deviation in liquid phase composition.

Table 7. Experimental and calculated binary azeotropic data for the 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) system.

Azeotropes						
	System (1) + (2)		System (1) + (3)		System (2) + (3)	
	x_1	T (K)	x_1	T (K)	x_2	T (K)
Exptl. data	0.438 ^a	360.90 ^a	-	-	0.248 ^b	335.05 ^b
NRTL	0.421	360.50	-	-	0.214	335.27
UNIQUAC	0.422	360.52	0.018	341.58	0.216	335.48

^a Iliuta et al.²³

^b Lladosa et al.²⁴

Table 8. Specification of the design variables in the azeotropic distillation process.

	Variables	Specification
<i>Feed stream</i>		
	Temperature (°C)	35
	Mass flow (kg/h)	1500
	1-propanol mass fraction	0.69
<i>Decanter</i>		
	Temperature (°C)	10 or 30
	Purity (water mass fraction)	0.96
<i>Azeotropic column</i>		
	Operation Pressure (kPa)	101.3
	Purity (1-propanol mass fraction)	0.99
	Recovery of 1-propanol (%)	99.0

Table 9. Optimum results for azeotropic distillation column with both decanter options; at 10°C (Option 1) and 30 °C (Option 2) of the decantation temperature.

	<i>Option 1</i>	<i>Option 2</i>
Ideal stages	20	29
Feed stage	17	25
Reflux Ratio	2.75	4.75
Reboiler heat duty (kJ/h)	$7.709 \cdot 10^6$	$1.840 \cdot 10^7$

Table 10. Utility prices^a

<i>Utility</i>	<i>Price</i>
Low pressure steam (€/t)	32.4
Processes cooling water (€/m ³)	0.017
Refrigerated water (€/m ³)	0.216

^aTurton et al.²⁷

Figures

Figure 1. Experimental VLLE diagram for 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3) ternary system at 101.3 kPa in mole fractions. Experimental data: ●, organic liquid phase; ■, aqueous liquid phase; ▲, vapor phase; ○, organic liquid phase (data from Piennar et al.¹⁰); □, aqueous liquid phase (data from Piennar et al.¹⁰); △, vapor phase (data from Piennar et al.¹⁰); ★, binary azeotrope; - - -, tie lines. Calculated data: solid line, binodal curve; - · - ·, vapor phase predicted by NRTL model with parameters from Table 4.

Figure 2. General azeotropic distillation sequence for 1-propanol – water separation with diisopropyl ether as entrainer.

Figure 3. Material balance lines for separation from a mixture of 1-propanol (1) + water (2) + diisopropyl ether (3): - - -, balance lines; - · -, tie lines; —, binodal curve.

Figure 4. Aspen Hysys process flow diagram (PFD) of azeotropic distillation sequence.

Figure 5. Reboiler heat duty Q , versus total number of stages N for both decanter options; ●, option 1 (10°C); ▲, option 2 (30°C).

Figure 6. Utilities costs for the different options of decantation temperature in the azeotropic distillation sequence. Option 1 at 10°C and Option 2 at 30 °C.

Azeotropic distillation for 1-propanol dehydration with diisopropyl ether as entrainer: equilibrium data and process simulation.

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Table S1. Number of stages N , optimal feed stage NF , reflux ratio RR and reboiler heat duty Q for the azeotropic column with a decantation temperature of 10°C.

N	NF	RR	Q (kJ/h)·10 ⁶
17	14	4.07	10.08
18	15	3.42	8.92
19	16	3.01	8.18
20	17	2.75	7.71
21	17	2.55	7.36
22	18	2.50	7.04
23	20	2.37	6.83
24	22	2.27	6.66
25	23	2.18	6.50
26	24	2.03	6.43
27	25	1.97	6.32
28	25	1.91	6.22
29	26	1.87	6.15
30	26	1.86	6.12
31	27	1.82	6.05
32	28	1.79	6.01

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Table S2. Number of stages N , optimal feed stage NF , reflux ratio RR and reboiler heat duty Q for the azeotropic column with a decantation temperature of 30°C.

N	NF	RR	Q (kJ/h)·10 ⁶
20	15	14.84	48.61
22	18	9.17	31.91
24	20	6.96	25.04
26	22	5.80	21.43
28	24	5.12	19.49
29	25	4.75	18.40
30	26	4.56	17.82
32	29	4.20	16.77
34	31	3.98	16.11
36	33	3.72	15.31
38	35	3.61	14.98
40	35	3.48	14.60